

CRITERIA FOR CLASSIFICATION OF COMMUNICATIVE EXERCISES

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ABSTRACT

Over the previous few decades, the field of second or world language education has seen many changes and trends. There have been other approaches that have come and gone. The Audiolingual Method, cognitive-based approaches, the Total Physical Response (TPR), and the Natural Physical Response (NPR) have all been seen. Furthermore, the proficiency and standards-based movements have influenced the way people think about education. [1, p34]

To collect the study's data, the researchers used the content analysis method. According to the findings, 75 of the 331 activities were classed as requiring students to speak in order to complete the assignment. The "understanding" component received the highest scores of all. The "genuine materials" and "spontaneity" characteristics, on the other hand, received the lowest marks. The exercises did not grow more communicative as the book proceeded, according to the findings. The study's findings also revealed that a large proportion of the activities do not adhere to communicative language teaching ideas that aim to improve students' speech skills. [3, p19-20]

Communicative activities include any activities that encourage and require a

learner to speak with and listen to other learners, as well as with people in the program and community. The objective of communicative activities is to gather information, break down boundaries, talk about oneself, and learn about the culture. Activities that are truly communicative, according to Morrow, have three features in common: information gap, choice, and feedback. An information gap exists when one person in an exchange knows something the other person does not.

The communicative approach encourages students to use all of the English pieces they know or can recall without fear of failure, and to try to communicate themselves with basic accuracy and fluency in order to accomplish their goals.

“Thus classroom activities typically have some of the following characteristics:

- They seek to develop students’ communicative competence through linking grammatical development to the ability to communicate. Grammar is not taught in isolation but often arises out of a communicative task, thus creating a need for specific items of grammar.
- They create the need for communication, negotiation and interaction through the use of appropriate activities.
- They provide opportunities for both inductive and deductive learning of grammar.
- They make use of content that connects to students’ lives and interests.
- They allow students to personalize learning by applying what they have learned to their own lives.
- Classroom materials typically make use of authentic texts to create interest and to provide valid models of language.” [2, p23-24]

The following are the most typical forms of communicative activities in English classes:

Information-Gap Activities

An vital thing of communication is the notion of information gap. This refers back to the truth that during reality, humans generally talk which will get records they do now no longer possess. This is called an information gap. In order to attain their purpose, college students use all their expertise in English, commonly in genuine conditions with one-of-a-kind functions which come to be non-public goals. Example : locating the variations among

images or asking and giving information approximately a timetable

Jigsaw Activities

These are also based on the information-gap principle. It can be done with students working individually or in groups; each group has part of the information needed to complete an activity. To complete the task they must communicate and fit the pieces together. Of course, communication must be done as in real life, meaningfully and with a constant time pressure.

Example: put the paragraphs/ the pictures in the right order

Task-completion activities

They encourage students to develop strategies for communication: rewording, requesting, clarification, questioning, giving and following simple, clear instructions, clarifying or describing. They take the form of puzzles, games, map-reading, and other kinds of classroom tasks in which the focus is on using one’s language resources to complete a task.

Example1: find the way on a map or dictate and write a text (“Wall dictation” as proposed by Scrivener in his Learning Teaching)

Information-gathering activities

Can be student-conducted surveys, interviews, and searches in which students are required to use their linguistic resources to collect information.

Example: Find someone who...:

Opinion-sharing activities

These are activities in which students are encouraged to compare values, opinions, or beliefs; they are also encouraged to express themselves, to exercise public speaking, to surpass shyness.

Example: ranking six qualities of themselves, decide on the four most important objects you couldn't imagine your life without ("The pyramid" as proposed by Scrivener) or decide on which side you are and share your arguments on different topics (the use of technology, the importance of recycling)

Information-transfer activities

"These require learners to take information that is presented in one form, and represent it in a different form." as mentioned by Nisrina Sesairiah in the study Communicative Language Learning Teaching Method. For example, in pairs, student A describes a village and student B draws a map of it or draws a picture of a place they have visited.

Reasoning-gap activities

These activities involve logical deduction skills and deriving some new information, finding similarities etc. For example, working out a teacher's timetable on the basis of given class timetables or organizing a goodbye party for a friend.

Role plays

Students are assigned roles and improvise a scene or exchange based on given information or presentations. Examples can be drawn from the real world to the imaginary one also from literature (a business meeting, a conversation in a plane, in a shop, an interview with an alien

and so on). Role play can vary into real-play or simulations.

Students should feel encouraged to speak and to improvise also. Of course, there will be problems with the shy students, but in time, if the activities are repeated and there is a positive environment they will feel more comfortable to express themselves. [2, p39-40]

It's also important to draw attention to the mistakes made, but it has been approved that feedback should be offered after the activity. For example, the teacher can write sentences containing different types of mistakes heard in students' conversations and ask them to come up and correct them. [2, p40]

Conclusion

As we've seen in practice, for every type, numerous communicative activities may be discovered from locating image variations to video games they may be tailored to numerous fashionable contexts aiming to broaden all capabilities and language systems. They contain coming across that lacking statistics or an statistics switch which comes as a reaction to a communicative want due to which college students will clearly warfare to surpass. Students learn how to speak and through doing this they learn how to be properly teammates or properly leaders, each cooperative and competitive, privy to their progress, their strengths and weaknesses.

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